

NDAC/LO/072

1986 May 28

16th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP8000: Double stars (Söderhjelm)

The simulation of double star observations and reductions has continued for close pairs (separation $< 1-2''$), for which the relative positions may not be known beforehand, or which are not previously known as double (C). An iteration scheme is proposed, by which a series of starting parameters is systematically searched for the "best" solution. This will usually converge towards the correct solution for $\rho < 1.2''$ and $\Delta m < 2.5$ mag.

Work currently in progress covers the intermediate range of separations, about 1.2 to 2.4 arcsec, where no particular problems were encountered, and systems with appreciably curved orbital motion.

The effect of a decreased slit width on double-star reductions was briefly investigated (C). A small decrease of the slit width ($< 10\%$) seems to have rather little effect on the determination of double-star parameters, to be compared with a rather significant deterioration previously found for a similar *increase* of the slit width (C212).

Miscellaneous (Lindegren)

A new format for exchanging results of the IDT counts simulations has been proposed (C).

Simulation of input data for the Set solution is being planned and a scheme was presented at the NDAC meeting at RGO on May 20-21. The complete simulation software package should be delivered to CUO/DSRI by September 1.

Working papers

- C Lindegren 1986 March 20: Format for exchanging results of IDT counts processing
- C Söderhjelm 1986 April 2: Influence of decreased slit-width on the (NDAC/LO/070) HIPPARCOS binaries
- C Södrehjelm 1986 April 28: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, II (NDAC/LO/071)